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Art has a mental health problem.

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shooter.

Annotation

This article sheds light on the extent to which the owners of the musical arts and Fine Arts Sox are more susceptible to depression than other professional owners-his sabaps and solutions. Since art is associated with the psyche, it is easier for him to face problems. In this article you can see exactly how to proceed in these cases. Of course all sohaningham have cases of depression of their own difficulties but when it comes to music or the field of Fine Arts, this situation develops a lot faster.

Keywords: Music art, depression, health, psyche.

Commissioned by Help Musicians UK and conducted by researchers Sally-Anne Gross and Dr George Musgrave at the University of Westminster, the study confirmed what anyone who has worked in music education already knows, music education can have a bad impact on your mental and physical health.

According to a study by the University of Westminster and MusicTank, musicians write that 2,211% of 68.5% experienced depression and 71.1% had severe anxiety or panic attacks. These results suggest that musicians are 3 times more prone to depression than the average person. The musicians, unfortunately, have moved away from society. While their friends have a good time, they spend countless hours honouring and performing their art. They do not have unstable working hours to communicate, establish strong ties with people, or maintain contacts due to their disorganization. Because musicians are so alienated from society, they often feel absent. Researchers Gross and Musgrave: this study is a decisive step in our understanding of the complex relationships that musicians have between working conditions and mental health conditions.

Since musicians often go on tour, in a healthy lifestyle, they have problems. Not sleeping in time eating disorders being on the road for a long time will also be fraught with depression. In addition, they are always away from their families, friends because they travel of course this state generates depression.

When artists are depressed abroad, they turn to drug and alcohol resistance organizations. Drugs and alcohol have always been in the music business, and their use has been popular with many artists. Drugs and alcohol are considered by many to be musicians or as part of their culture. This is bad because drugs and alcohol make depression worse. After musicians become addicted to drugs and alcohol as a coping mechanism, it becomes much more difficult for them not to be discouraged. This is bad not only for artists, but also for those in adulthood who have an impressive, intelligent mind.

Artists are now romanticizing depression and drugs because they find it useful. While some artists, such as Mac Miller, have indeed struggled with depression and drug addiction, some may describe doing it for money. After Lil Peep's death, his younger brother Karl Ahr mentioned how his death was an accident and that he was only depressed. He mentions his brother's depression and his vision as a quick way to deal with depression through drugs, which cost a long time for this condition. There is no false depression, unfortunately, we have lost many talented musicians and artists over the past few years due to depression and the brutal effects of drugs.

Early findings showed that while artists find solace in music production, working in the music industry can indeed make musicians sick or at least contribute to the extent of their mental illness. Respondents did this for a variety of reasons, including:

- Poor working conditions, including: difficulty ensuring survival, anti-social Working Time, fatigue, and inability to plan their time/future.
- Non-recognition of one's work and the transformation of music and identity into one's own idea of selfishness.
- Physical impact of a musical career, such as a violation of the musculoskeletal system.

List of literature.

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6. "Substance abuse and depression: dangerous down-Spiral."PsyCom.net -mental
7. Since 1986, the source of Health,
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